

Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä (2026)

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The primary goal of this project is to collect original early descriptions of the symptoms of scurvy, with an emphasis on firsthand clinical observations and historically significant accounts.

Motivations for collecting early reports on scurvy:

1. Many of the reports included here are of great historical interest. For example, during some long sea voyages more than half of the crew died from scurvy, with profound consequences for the outcome and success of such expeditions.
2. In his authoritative book *The History of Vitamin C and Scurvy* (1986), Kenneth Carpenter referred to numerous early reports. At that time, the sources were not available online. Many of the documents included in this collection provide direct access to reports cited by Carpenter.
3. Several early reports were written by physicians who had personally treated large numbers of patients with scurvy. Their extensive firsthand experience allowed them to describe a wide range of symptoms of scurvy in detail. As a result, many of these early descriptions can be much more informative for understanding the clinical spectrum of scurvy than many modern reviews, which often focus primarily on biochemical mechanisms.
4. Oranges, lemons, and other plants were known to prevent and cure scurvy long before the work of James Lind. This early knowledge represents an important and fascinating aspect of medical history. Moreover, recovery following the use of fruit and other plant foods strongly supports the conclusion that the observed symptoms were indeed caused by scurvy.

Short texts are presented in full, while longer works are shown as extracts with sufficient surrounding context to preserve meaning. Many of the original reports are difficult to access or challenging to read due to poor scan quality, gray backgrounds, low contrast, and old typefaces. To improve readability, several texts have been transcribed and reformatted using modern fonts. When available, links to the original digitized sources are provided in the listed documents.

The documents are arranged chronologically according to the year of the original report or observation, with the oldest first. In the case where a report describes events that occurred earlier than its publication date, the year of the event is used for placement. **Review articles** are indicated in bold. This list may be updated as additional relevant early texts are identified.

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<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=hemila+h+vitamin>

<https://scholar.google.fi/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/fi/persons/harri-hemil%C3%A4>

1218 Siege of Damietta

Jacques de Vitry's description of scurvy during the Fifth Crusade (1218-1219)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18338064>

1249 Siege of Cairo

Description of scurvy on the Seventh Crusade by *Jean de Joinville* (1249)

Joinville, Jean de

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17341537>

1498 Sea voyage /Oranges

Scurvy during *Vasco da Gama's* first voyage (1497-1499)

Ravenstein, Ernst Georg

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>

1500

1500 Sea voyage /Oranges, lemons

Scurvy during Pedro Álvares Cabral's voyage (1500)

Greelee, William

In: Voyage of Pedro Alvares Cabral to Brazil and India, p.65-66

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18785796>

1521 Sea voyage

Scurvy during *Magellan's* voyage around the world (1519-1522)

Pigafetta, Antonio

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>

1521 Sea voyage

Magellan's voyage around the world; English translation of Pigafetta by Richard Eden (1555)

Eden, Richard

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17999904>

1535 /Spruce ?

Scurvy on *Jacques Cartier's* second voyage to North America (Winter 1535-1536)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17348074>

1541

Description of scurvy by *Echtius* (1541)

Lind, James 1753

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093279>

1555 Sieges in general

Description of scurvy symptoms by *Olaus Magnus* (1555)

Hemilä, Harri

Korkiakangas, Timo

Chalker, Elizabeth

Zenodo 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13380745>

1567

Description of scurvy by *Wierus* (1567)

Lind, James 1753

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093229>

1564 /Oranges

Description of scurvy by *Ronsseus* (1564)

Lind, James 1753

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093314>

1579 Sea voyage

Scurvy during *Thomas Stevens'* voyage to India (1579)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174375>

1589

The first voyage of *Robert Baker* to Guinea, with the *Minion*, and *Primrose*, set out in October, 1562

[*The first use of term scurvy in English language in 1589*]

Hakluyt, Richard

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17941245>

1589

The voyage intended towards China, wherein M. Edward Fenton was appointed Generall, written by master Luke Ward his Vice admirall, and Captaine of the *Edward Bonaventure*, begun Anno Dom. 1582

[*The first use of term scurvy in English language in 1589*]

Hakluyt, Richard

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18175088>

1593 Sea voyage /Oranges

Scurvy during *Richard Hawkins'* voyage (1593)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>

1593 Sea voyage /Scurvy-grass
Scurvy on *John Davis'* voyage (1591-1593)
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884408>

1596 Sea voyage /Scurvy-grass
Two sailors with scurvy described by William Clowes (1596)
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18788642>

1600

1602 Sea voyage /Cactus: *Opuntia imbricata*
Scurvy during *Sebastián Vizcaíno*'s exploration (1602-1603)
Ascensión, Antonio de la
Wagner, Henry R (1929)
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18300855>

1602 Sea voyage
Scurvy during *Sebastián Vizcaíno*'s exploration (1602-1603) [Summary]
Lind, James 1772
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18301146>

1602 Sea voyage /Oranges
François Pyrard's description of scurvy during a sea voyage (1602-1603)
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18415628>

1604 Sea voyage
Scurvy during *Henry Middleton*'s Voyage (1604)
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18418006>

1607 /Oranges
Certain philosophical preparations of food and beverage for sea-men, in their long voyages
Platt, Hugh
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18860119>

1611 /Oranges, lemons
De La Warre's description of treating scurvy with oranges and lemons (1611)
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18860528>

1617 Instructions to sea voyages /Oranges
Description of scurvy symptoms by *John Woodall* (1617)
Hemilä, Harri
Chalker, Elizabeth
Zenodo 2024
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651214>

1619
Memoirs Concerning the Old and New Greenland
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18328015>

1624 Siege of Breda
Description of scurvy by *Vander Mye* (1624)
Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225428>

1626 /Lemon juice

John Smith recommended the use of lemon juice as a treatment for scurvy (1626)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623985>

1631 /Lemon juice

John Winthrop describes the treatment of scurvy with lemon juice (1631)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18619215>

1632

Two Journals: the First Kept by Seven Sailors in Greenland; the Second Kept by Seven Other Sailors at Spitzbergen, in the Years 1633 and 1634.

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18327404>

1645

Scurvy described by the *Faculty of Medicine at Copenhagen* (1645)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17227206>

1651

Description of scurvy symptoms by *Francis Glisson* (1651)

Glisson, Francis

In: *Treatise of the Rickets: Being a disease common to Children*, pp. 249–250, 1651

Zenodo 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10206723>

1667

Thomas Willis on scurvy (1667)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17226864>

1681

Scurvy described by *M. Dellon* (1681)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17223800>

1685

Thomas Sydenham on scurvy (1685)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17223929>

1696, 1706, 1736

William Cockburn on scurvy (1696, 1706, 1736)

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18874588>

1699

A relation of some strange and wonderful effects of the scurvey,
which happened at Paris in the Year 1699

Poupart, François

Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London, 26, 223–232, 1708

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16846396>

1700

1703 Siege of Thorn /Plants, vegetables
Description of scurvy by *Bachstrom* (1734)
Lind, James 1772
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225783>

1720, 1737 / oranges, scurvygrass, pickled cabbage
Description of scurvy by *Kramer* (1720, 1737)
Lind, James 1772
Hemilä, Harri
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17224830>

1730
Damiano Sinopeo on Scurvy in Cronstadt (1730-1733)
Lind, James 1772
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18334992>

1732
Description of scurvy in Vyborg by *Nitzsch* (1732, 1734)
Lind, James 1772
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17295494>

1739
John Cook on scurvy in Russia (1738-1739)
Lind, James 1772
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299869>

1740 Sea voyage
Scurvy on *Anson's* voyage round the world (1740-1744)
Lind, James 1772
Hemilä, Harri
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>

1746
Scurvy in Hudson's bay (1746-1747)
Ellis, Henry
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18379214>

1747
Description of scurvy in the Russian Army by *Nitzsch* (1747)
Lind, James 1772
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296086>

1750
M. Gmelin on scurvy (1736, 1750)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299505>

1762 Sea voyage / vegetables, lime juice, and syrup of garlic

A fatal scurvy in the East Indies (1762)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299146>

1764

Donald Monro on scurvy (1764)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299334>

1764

Lewis Rouppe on scurvy (1764)

Lind, James 1772

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302180>

1770

Observations on the scurvy

De Mertans, Charles

Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London 68, 661–680, 1778

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16846144>

1772

On the scurvy [English translation from Latin]

Rouppe, Lewis

In: Observations on diseases incidental to seamen, pp.102–275, 1772

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17227637>

1776

The Scurvy

van Swieten, Gerard

In The diseases incident to armies: With the method of cure, pp. 89–93, 138–150.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18872183>

1800

1800

Dr. Trotter, on Citric Acid

Trotter, Thomas

Medical and Physical Journal, 4(18), 154–156, 1800

Zenodo 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604543>

1801 Siege of Alexandria

Account of the scurvy

Larrey, Dominique Jean

In: Memoirs of Military Surgery and Campaigns of the French Armies, pp.383–396, 1814

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15582455>

1816

On Scurvy

Trotter, Thomas

The London Medical and Physical Journal, 35(206), 257–260, 1816

Zenodo 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931475>

1827

On the diseases which prevailed among the British troops at Rangoon

Waddell, G

Transactions of the Medical and Physical Society of Calcutta, 3, 240–280, 1827

Zenodo 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207344>

1831

Clinical Lecture [on Scurvy]

Elliotson, John

Lancet, 15(Feb 12), 649–655, 1831

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15863945>

1836

On haemorrhagic pericarditis [Abstract]

Seidlitz

The British and Foreign Medical Review, 1(1), 259–263, 1836

Zenodo 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175282>

1838

Lectures on the theory and practice of medicine: scorbutus

Hall, Marshall

Lancet, 30, 849–857, 1838.

Zenodo 2026

<https://zenodo.org/records/18622240>

1839

Remarks on the cause of scurvy and on the means by which it may be prevented in merchant ships

Budd, George

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15647274>

1840

Scurvy

Budd, George

The Library of Medicine, ed. Alexander Tweedie, Vol. V, pp.58–95, 1840

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>

1842 Sea voyage

Notes on the scurvy, as it appeared on board the U. S. Frigate Columbia, in her cruize around the World,—1838-'39-'40

Coale, Edward

American Journal of the Medical Sciences, 3(5; Jan 1), 68–77, 1842

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15640277>

1847

Remarks on morbus cardiacus (scorbutic pericarditis) and on paracentesis of the pericardium in the same

Kyber, A

Medicinische Zeitung Russlands 1847

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302903>

1848

On pericarditis scorbutica, and its treatment by paracentesis [Abstract]

Kyber, A

Ranking's Abstract, 7, 64–65, 1848

Zenodo 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175404>

1848 Sea voyage

Report on scorbutus, as it appeared on board the United States Squadron, blockading the ports in the gulf of Mexico, in the summer of 1846

Foltz, Jonathan Messersmith

American Journal of the Medical Sciences, 15(29; Jan), 38–58, 1848

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15640912>

1854

Reports made to the Board of Admiralty and the Board of Trade, on the subject of preparing lemon-juice to render it an efficacious anti-scorbutic

Burnett, William

Medical Times and Gazette, 30 (NS 9)(Dec 23), 635–636.

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18483342>

1858

Scurvy

Army Medical Department

In: Medical and Surgical History of the British Army Which Served in Turkey and the Crimea During the War Against Russia in the Years 1854-55-56. Vol. II, pp.171–186, 1858

Zenodo 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10103879>

1862

Health and hospitals in Mississippi

Rawson, Charles H

American Medical Times, 5(3), 42, 1862

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15581966>

1862

Land scurvy

Lyman, Francis R

American Medical Times, 5(9), 125, 1862

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15582118>

1862

Army correspondence [about scurvy]

Gibbs, OC

The Medical and Surgical Reporter, 9(3), 82–83, 1862

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15582180>

1866

Scurvy in the twenty-fifth army corps

Perry, Ira

The Boston Medical and Surgical Journal, 74(8), 155–157, 1866

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15582246>

1866

Observation on scurvy, and its causes among the U.S. colored troops of the 25th army corps, during the spring and summer of 1865

Hemenway, S

The Chicago Medical Examiner, 7(10), 582–587, 1866

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15582211>

1866

Camp diarrhoea [and scurvy]

Morse, DA

The Medical and Surgical Reporter, 15(14), 296–298, 1866

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15581894>

1871 Infant scurvy

A case of scurvy in a child

Ingerslev, V

Hospitals-Tidende, 14(31; Aug 2), 121–122, 1871

Zenodo 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15424739>

1873 Infant scurvy

Scurvy in a child ten months old

Jalland, WH
The Medical Times and Gazette, I(March 8), 248, 1873
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15373630>

1878

Scurvy, Scorbutus (German: Scharbock)
Immermann, H

In: Cyclopaedia of the Practice of Medicine, Ed. H von Ziemssen, vol. XVII, 105–242, 1878
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302867>

1881

On Osteal or Periosteal Cachexia
Gee, Samuel

Saint Bartholomew's Hospital Reports, 17, 9-12, 1881
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18662197>

1885

Scurvy
Hirsch, August

In: Handbook of Geographical and Historical Pathology, vol. II, pp.507–568, 1885
Zenodo 2023
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10104179>

1888

On Scurvy
United States Army

In: The Medical and Surgical History of the War of the Rebellion, (1861-65)
Part III, Vol. I., pp.683–715, 1888
Zenodo 2023
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10201743>

1891

Sicknesses of Voyages and Colonies (Sea Scurvy, Flux, Fever, and Yellow Fever.)
Creighton, Charles

In: A History of Epidemics in Britain, p.578-645.
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882745>

1892 Infant scurvy

Scorbutus in infants; American cases
Northrup, William P

Archives of Pediatrics, IX(1; Jan), 1–22, 1892
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463670>

1892 Infant scurvy

Scurvy
Barlow, Thomas

In: Cyclopædia of the Diseases of Children, vol. II, ed. JM Keating, pp.265–278, 1892
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15586834>

1894 Infant scurvy
Scorbutus in infants
Northrup, William P
Crandall, Floyd M
New York Medical Journal, LIX(May 26), 641–646, 1894
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463815>

1896
Scurvy
Stengel, Alfred
In: Twentieth Century Practice: An international Encyclopedia of Modern Medical Science, vol. VII, 491-514
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18622716>

1898
Scurvy
Thompson, W Gilman
In: A System of Practical Medicine, vol. IV, pp. 1053–1063
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18622503>

1898 Infant scurvy
The American pediatric society's collective investigation on infantile scurvy in North America
Griffith, JP Crozer
Jennings, Charles G
Morse, John Lovett
The Boston Medical and Surgical Journal, 138, 605–609 and 139, 3–5, 1898
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15373841>

1898 Infant scurvy
The American pediatric society's collective investigation on infantile scurvy in North America
American Pediatric Society
Archives of Pediatrics, 15(7), 481–508, 1898
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282390>

1900

1904

On the etiology of scurvy

Coplans, Myer

Transactions of the Epidemiological Society of London, 23, 79–116, 1904

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18621256>

1911 Infant scurvy

Scorbutus (Scurvy)

Holt, L Emmett

In: The Diseases of Infancy and Childhood, 6th p., pp.233–241, 1911

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15343352>

1912

Über experimentellen skorbut [in German]

Holst, Axel

Frölich, Theodor

Zeitschrift für Hygiene und Infektionskrankheiten, 72, 1–120, 1912

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8410010>

1914

The pathologic affinities of beriberi and scurvy

Darling, ST

JAMA, 63(15), 1290–1294, 1914

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10102994>

1915 Infant scurvy

Infantile scurvy

Still, George Frederic

In: Common Disorders and Diseases of Childhood, 3rd p., pp.108–122, 1915

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15342856>

1917 Infant scurvy

Infantile scurvy. V. A study of its pathogenesis

Hess, Alfred F

American Journal of Diseases of Children, 14(5), 337–353, 1917

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609522>

1918

The relative content of antiscorbutic principle in limes and lemons, together with some new facts and some old observations concerning the value of "lime juice" in the prevention of scurvy

Chick, Harriette

Hume, E Margaret

Skelton, Ruth F

Smith, Alice Henderson

Lancet, 192, Nov 30, 735-738

<https://zenodo.org/records/18543473>

1918

The heart in infantile scurvy [English translation from German]

Erdheim, J

Wiener klinische Wochenschrift, 31(49), 1293–1295, 1918

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7756493>

1918

Beer and scurvy: some notes from history

Smith, Alice Henderson

Lancet, 192, Dec 14, 813-815

<https://zenodo.org/records/18543205>

1919

Scurvy: A Disease Due to Absence of Vitamine

Harden, Arthur

In: Physiology and National Needs pp. 51–73

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623119>

1919

A historical inquiry into the efficacy of lime-juice for the prevention and cure of scurvy

Smith, Alice Henderson

Journal of the Royal Army Medical Corps, 32(Feb+Mar), 93–116, 188–208

<https://zenodo.org/records/18484405>

1919

Scurvy VIII. Factors affecting the antiscorbutic value of foods

Hess, Alfred F

Unger, Lester J

American Journal of Diseases of Children, 17(4), 221–240, 1919

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210367>

1919

The pathogenesis of deficiency disease. III.

The Influence of Dietaries Deficient in Accessory Food Factors on the Intestine

McCarrison, Robert

Indian Journal of Medical Research, 7, 167–187, 1919

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14416103>

1919

The pathogenesis of deficiency disease. IV.

The Influence of a Scorbutic Diet on the Adrenal Glands

McCarrison, Robert

Indian Journal of Medical Research, 7, 188–194, 1919

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14416275>

1919

Report on the Present State of Knowledge Concerning Accessory Food Factors (Vitamines)

Medical Research Committee

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18790418>

1919

Scurvy [English translation from German]

Bierich, R

Deutsches Archiv für klinische Medizin, 130(26 Sept), 151–171, 1919

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10653558>

1919 Infant scurvy

The deleterious effect of the alcalization of infant's food

Hess, Alfred F

Unger, Lester J

JAMA, 73(18), 1353–1356, 1919.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14866713>

1920 Infant scurvy

Scorbutic beading of the ribs

Hess, Alfred J

Unger, Lester J

American Journal of Diseases of Children, 19(5), 331–336, 1920

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10102674>

1920

The founders of Naval hygiene: Lind, Trotter, and Blane

Taylor, JS

U.S. Naval Medical Bulletin, 14(4), 563–628, 1920

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604304>

1921

The Vitamine Manual: a Presentation of Essential Data About the New Food Factors

Eddy, Walter H

Zenodo 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18789954>

1923 Infant scurvy

Infantile scurvy (Barlow's disease)

Hess, Alfred F

In: Pediatrics, vol. II, ed. Abt, pp.849–875, 1923

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15465662>

1924

Studies in Scurvy. Part I: Examination of the antiscorbutic value of some vegetable products

Höjer, J Axel

Acta Paediatrica, III(Supplement), 8–28, 1924

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661233>

1924

Studies in scurvy. Part II: Histo-pathological studies

Höjer, J. Axel

Acta Paediatrica, III(Supplement), 29–115, 1924

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661249>

1924

Studies in scurvy. Part III: Discussion of some scurvy problems

Höjer, J Axel

Acta Paediatrica, III(Supplement), 115–140, 1924

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661247>

1924

Studies in scurvy. Part IV: Scurvy and tuberculosis

Höjer, J Axel

Acta Paediatrica, III(Supplement), 140–171, 1924

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661245>

1924

Studies in scurvy. Part V: Records of cases

Höjer, J Axel

Acta Paediatrica, III(Supplement), 172–278, 1924

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661241>

1924

Studies in scurvy. Figures of histo-pathological examinations

Höjer, J Axel

Acta Paediatrica, III(Supplement), 1924

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661239>

1926

Intracellular substances in experimental scorbutus

Wolbach, S Burt

Howe, Percy R

Archives of Pathology, 1(1), 1, 1926

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526150>

1927

L'état actuel de nos connaissances sur les vitamines: Leur application a l'hygiène publique
[in French]

Funk, Casimir

Rev. d Hyg. et de Med. Prev., 49, 561–580, 1927

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14496889>

1928

The symptomatology and gross morphology of experimental scurvy in the guinea pig

Meyer, Arthur W

Stanford University Publications, University Series. Medical Sciences, II(2), 133–170, 1928

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661090>

1928

The minute morphology of experimental scurvy in the guinea pig

Meyer, Arthur W

Stanford University Publications, University Series. Medical Sciences, II(2), 171–195, 1928

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661167>

1928

Some characteristics of the blood of the guinea pig in experimental scurvy

McCormick, Lewis M

Stanford University Publications, University Series. Medical Sciences, II(2), 199–233, 1928

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661187>

1928

The association of bowel disease with vitamin C deficiency

Mackie, FP

Chitre, GD

Indian Journal of Medical Research, 16(1), 77–94, 1928

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14495925>

1931

Diätetik und tuberkulose unter besonderer berücksichtigung
des Kalkstoffwechsels und der Bedeutung der Vitamine [in German]

Stub-Christensen, V

Acta Tuberculosea Scandinavica (Kobenh.), 5, 235–263, 1931

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497159>

1932

Recent advances in knowledge of scurvy and the antiscorbutic vitamin

Hess, Alfred F

JAMA, 98(17), 1429–1433, 1932

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609694>

1932

Diet, nutrition and infection

Hess, Alfred F

New England Journal of Medicine, 207(15), 637–648, 1932

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609616>

1934

Pathologic changes in the organs of scorbutic guinea pigs

Bessey, Otto A

Menten, Maud L

King, CG

Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine, 31, 455–460, 1934

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695238>

1934

The vitamins and resistance to infection

Robertson, Elizabeth Chant

Medicine, 13(3), 123–206, 1934

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14496927>

1934

The influence of nutrition upon resistance to infection

Clausen, SW

Physiological Reviews, 14(3), 309–350, 1934

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497214>

1936

Cardiovascular and arthritic lesions in guinea-pigs
with chronic scurvy and hemolytic streptococcal infections

Schultz, Mark P

Archives of Pathology, 21, 472–495, 1936

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695321>

1936

Vitamin C in the treatment of pneumonia [English translation from German]

Gander, J

Niederberger, J

Münchener Medizinische Wochenschrift, 83(51), 2074–2077, 1936

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406760>

1937

Effect of acute scurvy on the guinea-pig heart

McBroom, Josephine

Sunderland, Douglas A

Mote, John R

Archives of Pathology, 23, 20–32, 1937

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695419>

1937
Erfahrungen mit vitamin C in der pneumoniebehandlung [in German]
Gunzel, W
Kroehnert, G
Fortschritte der Therapie, 11(8), 460–463, 1937
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10933115>

1937
Role of vitamin C in resistance
Perla, David
Marmorston, Jessie
Archives of Pathology, 23, 543–575 and 683–712, 1937
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14527877>

1937
Vitamin C in the treatment of croupous pneumonia [English translation from German]
Hochwald, A
Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift, 63(5), 182–184, 1937
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406698>

1937
Erfahrungen über die behandlung der lungenentzündung mit C-vitamin
[In German; Treatment of inflammation of the lungs with vitamin C]
Vogl, A
Münchener Medizinische Wochenschrift, 84, 1569–1572, 1937
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15202539>

1939
The therapeutic application of vitamin C in periodontal disease
Roff, F Stanley
Glazebrook, AJ
Journal of the Royal Naval Medical Service, 25, 340–348, 1939
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609923>

1940
Über den wert des C-vitamins in der behandlung einzelner akuter infektionskrankheiten
[in German]
Szirmai, Friedrich
Deutsches Archiv für klinische Medizin, 185, 434–443, 1940
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15202715>

1941
Scurvy
Eddy, Walter E
Dalldorf, Gilbert
In: The Avitaminoses: the Chemical, Clinical and Pathological Aspects of the Vitamin Deficiency Diseases 2 ed., 309-357.
Zenodo 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18789515>

1944
Some aspects of vitamin C metabolism
Farmer, Chester J

Federation Proceedings, 3, 179–188, 1944

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931307>

1944

Vitamin C economy in the human subject

Pijoan, Michel

Lozner, Eugene L

Bulletin of the Johns Hopkins Hospital, 75(5), 303–314, 1944

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931162>

1946

Severe scurvy: A clinical and hematologic study

Vilter, Richard W

Woolford, Robert M

Spies, Tom D

Journal of Laboratory and Clinical Medicine, 31(Jun), 609–630, 1946

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10203880>

1948

Virus pneumonia and its treatment with vitamin C

Klenner, Fred R

Southern Medicine and Surgery, 110(2), 36–38, 1948

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932789>

1949

Der tagesbedarf des erwachsenen an vitamin C

[in German: Adult requirements for vitamin C]

Scheunert, VA

International journal for vitamin and nutrition research 20, 374–386, 1949

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932392>

1951

Massive doses of vitamin C and the virus diseases

Klenner, Fred R

Southern Medicine and Surgery, 113(Apr), 101–107, 1951

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14495005>

1953

Editor's foreword

Stewart, CP

Guthrie, Douglas

In: Lind's Treatise on Scurvy: A Bicentennial Volume 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604636>

1953

The third edition of the [James Lind's] treatise

Stewart, CP

In: Lind's Treatise on Scurvy: A Bicentennial Volume 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604737>

1953

The Lind tradition in the Royal Naval Medical Service

Dudley, Sheldon

In: Lind's Treatise on Scurvy: A Bicentennial Volume 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10605143>

1953

James Lind and some of his contemporaries

Guthrie, Douglas

Meiklejohn, AP

In: Lind's Treatise on Scurvy: A Bicentennial Volume 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10605213>

1953

Vitamin C requirement of human adults: Introduction, General Plan, Case Histories, References

Bartley, W

Krebs, HA

O'Brien, JRP

This text contains the case reports of the participants of the final report of the Sheffield study (1953) which examined the requirement for vitamin C.

Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB), 280, 73–88, 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661782>

1953

Vitamin C requirement of human adults: Concise Account of the Experiment and Summary

Bartley, W

Krebs, HA

O'Brien, JRP

This is sections "Concise Account of the Experiment" "Summary" of the final report of the Sheffield study (1953) which examined the requirement for vitamin C.

Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB), 280, 1–21 and 143–144, 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14628064>

1953

Vitamin C requirement of human adults: Diet

Bartley, W

Krebs, HA

O'Brien, JRP

This is section "Diet" of the final report of the Sheffield study (1953) which examined the requirement for vitamin C.

Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB), 280, 56–69, 1953

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14628199>

1960

Can water-soluble vitamins be over-dosed? Research on vitamin C [induced scurvy in guinea pigs]

Gordonoff, T

Schweizerische medizinische Wochenschrift, 90(Jul 2), 726–729, 1960

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11066294>

1967

Colored precipitation reaction of the urine according to Kimbarowski (FARK)

as an index of the effect of ascorbic acid during treatment of viral influenza

[English translation from German]

Kimbarowski, JA

Mokrow, NJ

Deutsche Gesundheitswesen, 22(51), 2413–2418, 1967

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7116182>

1970

Ascorbic acid in the complex therapy of acute pneumonia

[English translation from Russian]

Mochalkin, NL
Voенno-meditsinskii zhurnal, 9, 17–21, 1970
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7097483>

1974
Health problems and vitamin C in Canadian Northern Military operations
Sabiston, Brian H
Radomski, Manny W
Defence Research Board, Department of National Defence.
DCIEM REPORT NO. 74-R-1012, 1974
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7303680>

1974 Same data as in 1970
Vitamin C metabolism during the treatment of acute pneumonia with antibiotics
[English translation from Russian]
Mochalkin, NL
Klinicheskaiia meditsina, 52(12), 61–65, 1974
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7097562>

1975 Same data as in 1970
Vitamin C requirement in patients with acute pneumonia during treatment with antibiotics
[English translation from Russian]
Mochalkin, NL
Vrachebnoe delo, 9, 88–92, 1975
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7097591>

1977
On a substance that can make us sick (if we do not eat it!)
Szent-Gyorgyi, Albert
Executive Health, XIII(9), 1–6, 1977
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14671493>

1978
How new understandings about the biological function of ascorbic acid
may profoundly affect our lives!
Szent-Gyorgyi, Albert
Executive Health, XIV(8), 1–4, 1978
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14627378>

1981
The War Years (1939-1945)
Krebs, Hans
Martin, Anne
In: Reminiscences and Reflections, pp.119–125, 1981
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14866789>

1988
Ascorbic acid, carnitine and fatigue
Hughes, R Elwyn
Medical Science Research, 16(14), 721–723, 1988
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932709>

1991
Vitamin C.
Panel on Dietary Reference Values

In: Dietary reference values for food energy and nutrients for the United Kingdom. Report of the Panel on Dietary Reference Values of the Committee on Medical Aspects of Food Policy Reports on Health and Social Subjects, 41, 117–122, 1991
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946536>

1994

The clinical effects of vitamin C supplementation in elderly hospitalised patients with acute respiratory infections

Hunt, C

Chakravorty, NK

Annan, G

Habibzadeh, N

Schorah, CJ

International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research, 63(3), 212–219, 1994

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406235>

1997

Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to the common cold

Hemilä, Harri

British Journal of Nutrition, 77(1), 59-72, 1997

<https://zenodo.org/records/18340043>

2000

2003

Scurvy in pediatric patients: a review of 28 cases

Ratanachu-Ek, Suntaree

Sukswai, Pisit

Jeerathanyasakun, Yongyot

Wongtapradit, Lawan

Journal of the Medical Association of Thailand, 86(Suppl 3), S734–S740, 2003

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7756608>

2006

Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections?

Hemilä, Harri

<https://zenodo.org/records/6395596>

2007

Vitamin C may affect lung infections

Hemilä, Harri

Louhiala, Pekka

Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine, 100(11), 495-498, 2007

<https://zenodo.org/records/18339295>

2017

Vitamin C and Infections

Hemilä, Harri

Nutrients, 9(4), 339, 2017

<https://zenodo.org/records/18339873>

2023

Abrupt termination of vitamin C from ICU patients may increase mortality: secondary analysis of the LOVIT trial

Hemilä, Harri

Chalker, Elizabeth

European Journal of Clinical Nutrition, 77(4), 490-494, 2022

<https://zenodo.org/records/18339187>

2024

The symptoms of vitamin C deficiency. 1.

Observations and descriptions by Hess, Lind, Trotter and Blane

Hemilä, Harri

Zenodo 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

2024

Vitamin C deficiency can lead to pulmonary hypertension: a systematic review of case reports

Hemilä, Harri

de Man, Angelique ME

BMC Pulmonary Medicine 24(1), 140, 2024

<https://zenodo.org/records/17549428>

2024

Rebound effect explains the divergence in survival after 5 days in a controlled trial on vitamin C for COVID-19 patients

Hemilä, Harri

Chalker, Elizabeth
Frontiers in Medicine, 11, 1391346, 2024
<https://zenodo.org/records/18339734>

2024

Vitamin C for patients with sepsis?
Hemilä, Harri
Chalker, Elizabeth
Frontiers in Medicine, 11, 1450091, 2024
<https://zenodo.org/records/18339641>

2025

Vitamin C for the common cold and pneumonia
Hemilä, Harri
Chalker, Elizabeth
Polish Archives of Internal Medicine, 135(1), 16926, 2025
<https://zenodo.org/records/18339256>

2025

Effect of vitamin C deprivation on the duration of colds in the Sheffield study (1953):
a statistical analysis
Hemilä, Harri
Zenodo 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717360>

2026

Are the UK's vitamin C recommendations evidence-based? A critical comment
Hemilä, Harri
Chalker, Elizabeth
British Journal of Nutrition, 2025
<https://zenodo.org/records/18339496>